

THERMAL CYCLING AND MOISTURE EFFECTS ON CREEP RECOVERY IN CFRP

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ABSTRACT

A linear viscoelastic theory was developed which predicts recovery strains in carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) as a function of creep loads, loading and unloading times, ply orientations, and general laminae properties. This paper combines this theory with non-linearizing parameters to characterize the effects of increased moisture content and matrix microcracking, such as is caused by thermal cycling to low temperatures. Experimental data are provided by axial compression of thin walled laminated tubes, with emphasis on measurement of recovery strains after short term loading. It is shown that moisture and microcracking alter the nonlinear materials parameters in different ways, and that both the magnitude and shape of the recovery curves are affected. The effect of moisture is to shift recovery curves to higher strain values, while the effect of internal damage can be described by a stress dependent exponential term.

INTRODUCTION

Recovery after short term creep tests at successively higher loadings defines the standard microyield strength test. In the case of viscoelastic materials, it can be used to define the stress level (applied for a time t_1) needed to cause a residual strain after a given time of unloading ($t - t_1$). A method of prediction of recovery strains (e_r) as a function of creep loads, times, ply orientations, and general laminae properties was developed.^{1,2} It was based on linear viscoelasticity of the matrix, and applies at low loads, low moisture contents and minor degrees of internal damage. An extension of this theory is required because of the well known sensitivity of creep and recovery data to internal damage.³ Creep and recovery data are often reported for "pre-conditioned" or "stabilized" composites to achieve agreement with non-linear viscoelastic theories, but a measure of change in properties is thereby lost.

It is known that viscoelastic non-linearizing parameters such as g_0 , g_1 , g_2 and the time shift factor "a"⁴ are functions of stress, temperature, and ply orientation and possibly moisture content changes, but it is not apparent that they can be used to predict the effects of matrix microcracking. For the response to stress alone (with different composite systems), g_2 can either decrease or increase or both.⁴⁻⁷ g_2 has also been expressed empirically as a hyperbolic sine function of stress.^{7,8}

THEORY

We recall that the total linear creep curve is^{1,2}

$$\epsilon(t) = \Delta e(t) + e_0 = Nm/A(t) \quad (1)$$

where

$$m = (1 - A_{12}^2 A_{11}^{-1} A_{22}^{-1})^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$\Delta e(t)$ is the measured creep, and equals zero at $t = 0$. The initial elastic deformation $e_0 = A'N$, where A' is the pertinent term of the totally inverted laminate stiffness matrix, readily calculated from the static laminae properties. N is the stress resultant ($N = P/w = h \sigma$, where h and w are the thickness and width dimensions perpendicular to the applied load, P). $A(t)$ is the time dependent in-plane laminate stiffness. To compute the recovery curve for a laminate we first measure the linear creep curves ($\Delta e(t)$) for three laminates of arbitrary layup of the same material. Equation 1 is used to obtain $A(t)$ for each of these, which in turn yields three equations of the type

$$A(t) = K_1 E_{xx}(t) + K_2 E_{yy}(t) + K_4 y(t) \quad (3)$$

$y(t)$ is a lumped parameter combining $E_{yy}(t)$, $\nu_{12}(t)$, and $G_{12}(t)$. The invariants K_1 , K_2 , and K_4 are calculated from their respective ply orientations. Matrix operations are used to compute the time dependent laminae constants $E_{xx}(t)$, etc. A new laminate layup requires a new set of invariants and the equation (3) is used in reverse to calculate $A(t)$ and $A(t - t_1)$. The (incremental) recovery strain after each loading is then given by:

$$e_r(t) = N m [(1/A(t)) - (1/A(t - t_1))] \quad (4)$$

Since these predictions are based on creep curves in the linear viscoelastic region, deviations due to high loads, microcracking or high humidity require modifications. (There are secondary effects also through possible reductions in the transverse stiffness but their effect on the parameter "m" is minimal.) An approach based on Lou and Schapery's equations⁴ starts by equating the general expression for nonlinear creep with Eq. (1);

$$\Delta e(t) = g_1 g_2 C (\psi)^n \sigma = Nm/A(\psi) - g_0 A'N \quad (5)$$

where

$$\psi = t_1/a + t - t_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \psi_1 = t_1/a \quad (6)$$

The recovery strain is given by

$$e = (\Delta e_1/g_1) [(1 + a \lambda)^n - (a \lambda)^n] \quad (7)$$

where $\lambda = (t - t_1)/t_1$. Values of "a," and "n" can be found from recovery data. Setting $\Delta e_1/g_1$ initially to 1, $\log e_r$ is plotted against λ for various values of "n." The actual e_r data are plotted on the same graph and the lowest level stress data are shifted vertically until a match is found for "n." The ratio $\Delta e_1/g_1$ is obtained from the master curve of e_r versus t by vertical shifting of recovery curves after the initial horizontal shift to get "a." The general equation for e_r ,

$$e_r = g_2 C \sigma [\psi^n - (\psi - \psi_1)^n] \quad (8)$$

is evaluated at t_1 (where $e_r = e'$) and low stress levels (where $g_2 = 1$) and thus may be used to calculate C . g_0 is found from the measured stress strain curves on loading and comparing these to predicted $A'N$ values.

EXPERIMENTAL

Thin walled angle-ply composite cylinders of pitch-based P75 graphite fiber reinforced Fiberite 934 epoxy resin were subjected to axial compression loading for 45 seconds, followed by recovery strain measurements using an LVDT. Layups studied were $(\pm 10)_s$, $(\pm 30)_s$, $(\pm 45)_s$, and $(\pm 80)_s$. After recovery times of 1800 s, loading increased by 8.28 MPa (200 lb) increments to 82.8 MPa. The samples in the as-fabricated condition were stabilized at room temperature and 50% relative humidity.

The high moisture samples were stabilized at 65°C and 80% R.H. over a 6-day period, with a net weight gain of 0.19%. From the data of Ref. 5, this suggests the moisture content of the samples increased from about 0.7 to 0.9 wt%, with the resin matrix content increasing from 2 to 2.6%. Matrix microcracking was inferred from ten cycles of quenching in liquid nitrogen with immersion for 300 s. Separate, non-preconditioned samples were used for each condition.

RESULTS

Data include plots of $\log e_r$, (for $t_1 = 45$ s, and $t = 90$ and 300 s), n , a , and g_2 versus stress for each layup and each condition (as-fabricated, added moisture, or thermally cycled). g_0 , the ratio of measured elastic strain to the strain (at the same load) of the as-fabricated samples was also determined.

Figure 1, for a $(\pm 45)_s$ layup, shows that the moisture curve has the same slope as the as-fabricated material curve, but is vertically displaced to higher e_r levels. The curve for the thermally cycled condition agrees with the as-fabricated curve up to a given stress level (about 25 MPa) and then a rapid increase in e_r . The results for $(\pm 30)_s$ showed similar results, except that the thermally cycled curve deviated only above 60 MPa. With a $(\pm 80)_s$ or $(\pm 10)_s$ layup, there was no effect of thermal cycling but a bigger moisture effect (Fig. 2).

The non-linear parameters a and g_2 both decrease from unity above a certain stress level for all layups and all conditions. The "a" shift factor decreased gradually above 35 MPa for the as-fabricated condition and above 25 MPa with enhanced moisture, but near 80 MPa, the values were similar for all layups. Thermal cycling showed a substantial drop in "a" and g_2 , except for the ± 80 layup. g_2 showed little overall change due to thermal cycling, but a substantial drop due to moisture. At low stress levels, there was a noticeable increase above unity for the moisture case (Fig. 3).

For the moisture exposure, g_0 increases slightly with increasing ply angle to 45°, and the results at $\pm 80^\circ$ are similar to those at $\pm 10^\circ$. The trend for microcracking is similar, but much more pronounced at the 45° angle. This would be expected at an essentially cross-ply layup, where the ply stresses are highest.¹⁰

Fig. 1 Variation of axial creep recovery strain at $t = 90$ s with successive 45 s loadings to higher stress levels. □ = as-fabricated, + = thermally cycled and ♦ added moisture. Ply orientation is $(\pm 45)_s$.

Fig. 2 Same as Fig. 1 for a ply orientation of $(\pm 80)_s$.

Fig. 3 Variation of the non-linear parameter g_2 with axial (0°) stress level for loading time $t_1 = 45$ s. $\square = (\pm 10)_s$, $+$ = $(\pm 30)_s$, $\diamond = (\pm 45)_s$, and $\Delta = (\pm 80)_s$.

ANALYSIS

Equation (8) shows that a decrease in g_2 decreases the predicted recovery strain, e_r , while a decrease in "a" increases it. Since these parameters both decrease with high stress, moisture, and microcracking levels, it is difficult to attribute any particular mechanism to their effect on e_r .

The linear relations of Figs. 1 and 2 imply that

$$e_r = d \exp(b \sigma), \text{ and } \log e_r = \log d + (b/2.303) \sigma \quad (9)$$

Moisture changes the level of recovery strain ("d" increases) while microcracking changes the slope "b." This implies also that there is no precise departure from linear to non-linear behavior. The resulting modification to the linear equation for recovery strain, Eq. (4), is

$$e_r = Q N m [(1/A(\psi) - 1/A(\psi - U_1))] \exp \{(b'_c + b'_o) N\} \quad (10)$$

where Q is related to the moisture content and the term in brackets accounts for the decreasing recovery strain with time after t_1 . The term $b' = (b'_c + b'_o) = b/h$ to allow consistent use of the stress resultant N. b'_o represents the non-linearizing effect of high stresses and b'_c represents the effect of internal damage. Figure 4 shows the variation of b' with ply angle. As $b' \rightarrow 0$, we have the linear viscoelastic prediction, except for the shift factor "a" in the Ψ term (Eq. (6)). We have found that the shape of the recovery curve as well as its magnitude is changed by moisture and internal damage, and this is handled by using $A(\Psi)$ instead of $A(t)$. The effect is equivalent to using reduced time dependent laminae moduli in Eq. (4). Equation (10) was found to give excellent predictions of the actual recovery curves, such as the measured e_r levels at $t = 300$ s for the various conditions.

Fig. 4 Variation of b' with ply angle orientation θ .

Fig. 5 Variation of lumped parameter (QN) with ply angle orientation.

Figure 5 shows that the combined term QN decreases slightly with increasing ply angle unless moisture is added. The e_r level is then shifted above the as-fabricated or microcracked state. The effect of Q on Eq. (10) is similar to g_2 . It is less obvious that internal damage or microcracking can be described by viscoelastic parameters and thus the empirical use of the exponential term would seem justified. The four non-linearizing parameters Q, "a," b'_c , and b'_o and the previous linear theory are then sufficient to predict the magnitude with time of any recovery curve.

Further work is in progress to express Q and b'_c in terms of the amount of moisture and internal damage, respectively.

The theory treats each creep/recovery curve as independent. Since each recovery curve was held for 1800 s, they were essentially flat to within experimental strain sensitivity (about 10^{-7}), so this is a reasonable assumption. Periodic tests to an initially high load gave identical results to the step wise loadings. With shorter times, however, and especially at high loads, the residual recovery curve from the previous loading should be taken into account. With microcracked samples there is also the question of further damage (crack) growth during the test.

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